

IMPACT OF MODERN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *In the modern process of humanization of society, the understanding of a person as a value in itself, which cannot act as a means for someone, but can only be a goal, and for society - an end in itself of social development, the problem of educating a person as a person capable not only of mastering the values of culture, and able to navigate the system of social values, but also to be the subject of his life, the strategist of his own destiny, which means to be responsible, including for personal safety.*

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The goal category is one of the most important in philosophy. The goal is considered as one of the elements of human activity, transformation of the surrounding world, as an ideal anticipation of the result of activity.

In teaching, the goal is a kind of intermediate link between the social and the methodical. Teaching foreign languages pursues a comprehensive implementation of practical, educational, educational and developmental goals: at the same time, educational, educational and developmental goals are achieved in the process of practical mastery of a foreign language.

"A truly comprehensive approach to learning goals, as E.I. Passov notes, requires the introduction of all aspects as components of the goal on equal rights (education, cognition, development)."

Only in this case, the training system should include special means to achieve these components of the goal. "On equal rights" means an even distribution of time on all aspects, and their equality is only in terms of importance for the formation of the student's personality.

Neglect of any aspect leads to tangible losses; the cognitive aspect does not develop motivation, the developmental aspect does not facilitate the process of mastering speech skills, the educational aspect of the goal is also not realized.

Let's take a closer look at the concept of the educational process. In the modern process of humanization of society, the understanding of a person as a value in itself, which cannot act as a means for someone, but can only be a goal, and for society - an end in itself of social development, the problem of educating a person as a person capable not only of mastering the values of culture, and able to navigate the system of social values, but also to be the subject of his life, the strategist of his own destiny, which means to be responsible, including for personal safety. Education is the purposeful organization of the pupil's interaction with the outside world at the level of achievements of modern culture.

What principles formed the basis of the educational process?

1. Taking into account the social situation of the child's development;
2. Turning education into a continuous innovation process;
3. Rejection of the idea that it is possible to change a child's life. The only thing that a teacher can do is to help a little person make a choice in a particular situation at the cultural level.

The goal of the value interaction process organized by the teacher is to move towards an unfixated result. The "measure of movement", the comprehension of cultural values will be different for each student. The only thing that a student is not allowed to do is stop, lack of development. Constant comprehension of Goodness, Beauty, Truth. The result of the school's activity is the education of a person who is ready for constant change, the development of human culture, able, based on the assimilation of modern culture, to continue the baton of generations.

In this regard, the following system of measures may be proposed.

Moral culture, like all social culture, has two main aspects:

- 1) values
- 2) regulations.

A didactic game in a foreign language lesson helps a child to realize important moral signs of communication, such as kindness, love for one's neighbor, mutual assistance. Games-competitions, travel games, training games, game situations, association games, games that develop certain mental processes: memory, observation, attention, reaction speed. In the game, the child learns to use the acquired knowledge in new conditions that activate him as much as possible, thereby helping him to better consolidate the acquired material. This form of work supports children's interest in learning, develops it. The didactic game keeps children's attention on one subject for quite a long time, it is emotionally saturated. Participating in it, the child experiences excitement, joy from a successfully completed task, chagrin over failure, a desire to test his strength anew. The game can be called a method of children's joy in fostering a positive attitude to learning.

Exercises with keys for self-control can be used for independent work in pairs and individual work in the classroom. Or one of the students of each pair receives the text of the exercise (stimuli and samples of reactions to them, that is, keys) and acts as a teacher, the second – as a student. After completing half of the exercise, they switch roles. When working independently in the classroom, the student himself reads the stimuli one by one and, without looking into the text, reacts to them, and then checks his answer with the key. When learning a foreign language, such forms of work give good results:

- a) competitions between two teams, including various tasks, including the staging of a dialogue;
- b) thematic conferences on the development of conversational skills using ICT, visual aids, additional literature;
- c) thematic conferences, the purpose of which is to summarize the results of the front reading.

Pedagogical contact is inextricably linked with such a component of modern methodological and pedagogical norms as the successful interaction of teachers and students in academic work.

The age-related needs of adolescents in the development of generalized methods of mental activity are met by all those forms of work that involve hierarchy and cause- and -effect dependencies of information elements, the allocation of the main thing, etc. Schoolchildren are characterized by such a state of mind as the expectation of communication, the search for communication. They see it as proof of their social and human value. In such conditions of personal self-expression, a real speech task arises, as well as a communicative motivation that ensures a person's proactive participation in communication.

Thus, the choice of rational forms of organization of the educational process is of paramount importance. Often the teacher sees two aspects: how is the assimilation of the program and what is the behavior of the child. There was an unequal substitution of education and training. Valeologists, physiologists, hygienists, believe that the child needs to be seen as a whole; his mental, physical and functional state. It is necessary to take into account the influence of the whole complex of factors.

External - social living conditions, ecology, school impact, pedagogical impact.

Internal - health, changes at each age stage; the load associated with schooling should correspond to the capabilities of a growing organism.

The educational process itself is built more often without taking into account physiology and hygiene. The division of children into groups (strong and weak) generates social maladaptation. Creating a situation of "joy", "success", emotional and psychological support in school, classroom is a requirement of time. It is important to implement health-saving technologies in the educational process: lessons should be built taking into account the age-related physiological characteristics of children with frequent changes of activity and physical training minutes, dynamic pauses. In order to strengthen and preserve the health of students and to form the necessary skills of a healthy lifestyle, sanitary and hygienic requirements should be systematically fulfilled (ventilation of the office, compliance with the light regime, etc.); take into account the hygienic conditions of the office, pay attention to the correct seating of students during the lesson, take into account the recommendations of the medical worker of the educational institution. We must remember that there is no ideal methodology. Children are so different, their individual characteristics are so obvious and significant that it is always necessary to remember that only the idea can be one, and the tactics and teaching methods should be different.

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